

The Influence of Parents' Role and Schools on The Learning Motivation of Class V Students at SDN 091607 Sinaksak

Lenny Imelda Kristina Marbun , Natalina Purba, Lisbet N. Sihombing
Universitas HKBP Nommensen Pematang Siantar, Indonesia

Corresponding author: Lenny Imelda Kristina Marbun;
lennyimeldachristinamarbun@gmail.com

A R Q I C L E I N F O

ABSTRACT

Keywords: Influence of Parents and School, Learning Motivation, Sd Negeri 091607

Received : 5, August

Revised : 12, September

Accepted: 17, October

©2023 Marbun, Purba, Sihombing: This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Atribusi 4.0 Internasional](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

This research aims to determine the influence of the role of parents and schools on the learning motivation of fifth grade students at SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak. The method used in this research is the quantitative method. The sample used was 33 students, in the research there were: the dependent variable (x) student learning motivation, and the independent variable (y) the influence of the role of parents. The data collection technique is the test technique. Test results using the Hypothesis test technique with the help of the SPSS program, based on the results of a significance calculation of 0.000. Because significance is smaller than 0.05, H₀ is rejected. Which means there is a significant influence between the school environment and the learning motivation of class V students at SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak. n significant value for the relationship of variable (x) simultaneously to y is $0.00 < 0.05$ and the f_{count} value is $27.947 > 4.20$ (f table) so it can be concluded that the hypothesis test is accepted which means there is a relationship between variables (x) simultaneously on the variable (y).

INTRODUCTION

Education is conscious guidance from educators towards the development of students' learning towards the formation of humans who have personalities. John Dewey said that education is a process of forming fundamental basic abilities, which involve thinking power. From the statement above, education is a conscious effort carried out through regular step-by-step procedures to suit educational goals.

Learning is one of the needs and activities of students to achieve change in themselves. The aim of implementing learning activities³ is to change the potential and behavior of students in a more positive direction. This change occurs because students in carrying out these activities experience a series of training processes and experiences gained in learning. Children's primary responsibility at school is learning and the most basic help parents can give is encouraging their children to learn and perform to the best of their abilities. Students who have strong motivation will have a lot of energy to study.

The quality of a student's learning will determine his learning achievement. The better the quality of a child's learning, the better his learning achievement will be. Learning achievement is a child's effort or activity to master the learning materials provided by the teacher at school. Students' learning achievements show that they have experienced a learning process and have experienced changes, whether changes in knowledge, skills or attitudes. Thus, a student is said to have good learning achievement, if the student has experienced changes, such as from initially not knowing to knowing, increasing skills and so on. There are still many students whose learning scores are still below the standards implemented by the school, so efforts are needed to improve student learning achievement.

In this case, it is a record of why this happened, because of the role of parents in involving themselves in their children's daily learning. Based on the problem of the role of parents on students' learning motivation. Based on the problems above, the research was interested in taking the research title "The Influence of the Role of Parents on the Learning Motivation of Class V Students at State Elementary School 091607 Sinaksak for the 2023/2024 Academic Year".

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The important role of parental attention in the family environment is to provide first experiences during childhood. That's because first experiences are an important factor in personal development and ensure a child's emotional life. In essence, every parent has the hope that their children will grow and develop into good and pious children, so that they will not fall into acts that can harm themselves or others. These hopes would be easier to realize if parents were aware from the start of their role as parents, having to pay attention to their children every day, no matter how busy they are, don't forget to control and educate their children, give them love and provide guidance. Apart from that, the influence of the role of parents is one of the external factors that influences student learning outcomes. Parents who pay attention to their children by guiding, supervising, and providing learning tools can also improve student learning achievement. Student discipline and the influence of parents' roles mutually influence student learning achievement. The influence of discipline is not temporary, but will last forever. Parents must also support students by approaching and instilling discipline in students.

Parents can motivate students to continue studying at home. It is hoped that this research will be able to improve students' learning discipline and parents will be aware of the importance of the influence of parents' role on children's learning development so that children's learning outcomes improve. Based on these thoughts,

the pattern of thinking in research can be described as follows. Regarding the learning motivation achieved by their children at school, almost all parents hope that their children will achieve high learning achievements at school. However, parents tend to be resigned by stating that their child's motivation to learn is more due to the abilities of the child in question. From the description above, it is hoped that there will be a relationship between the influence of the role of parents and student learning motivation.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

The type of research used in this research is quantitative research. According to Sugiyono (2017:72), quantitative research is research based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, data collection using research instruments, quantitative/statistical data analysis, with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses. This research aims to find out whether there is an influence of parental attention on students' thematic learning outcomes.

The population used was all students at state elementary school 091607 Sinaksak and the sample used was 33 students. The research instrument used is a questionnaire, the instrument tests used are validity tests, reliability tests, hypothesis tests, data collection techniques use observation, interviews, observation notes, data analysis techniques use data presentation, drawing conclusions, descriptive statistics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Instrument Test Results

1. Questionnaire Validity Test

The instrument in this research is a questionnaire containing 25 questions. The questionnaire is used to determine the variable (X), namely the Role of Parents and Schools to find students' learning motivation at school.

This test is carried out by calculating the amount of $r_{\text{calculated}}$ using the *Pearson product monen* formula which is compared with r_{table} if $r_{\text{calculated}} > r_{\text{table}}$ then the instrument can be used to collect data, and the instrument used must be valid and the instrument is invalid

Validity can be seen and it can be concluded that the rcount for each question item is greater than the rtable, (rcount for each question item > 0.361) so it can be concluded that the questionnaire used by the researcher in collecting data is valid.

2. Validity Test Results Student learning motivation

To test validity, researchers used the SPSS program. For the level of validity, a significant test was carried out by comparing the r_{count} with the value r_{table} which if r_{count} is greater than r_{table} then the statement item is said to be valid. From the validation above, it can be concluded that the r_{count} for each statement item is greater

than 0.361, namely r_{table} . So it can be concluded that the questionnaire used by researchers in collecting data is valid.

1. Questionnaire Reliability Test

Table 1 SPSS Reliability Test

Variable	Alpha	Information
X	0.826	Reliable

Based on table 4.4 above, you can see that $r_{table} = 0.826$ and $r_{table} = 0.361$, so $r_{count} > r_{table}$ and *Crobach's Alpha* $0.826 > 0.50$. From the reliability test calculations, there is parental attention to students' learning motivation at school, it can be concluded that this research instrument is reliable and highly interpretable.

2. Prerequisite Test Results

a. Normality test

Testing was carried out to determine whether the research data used was normally distributed or not, using Kolmogorov analysis (*one sample test*) the data was processed using SPSS version 26. The data used for data normality were the results of questionnaire scores and monthly scores which had been prepared by researchers as instruments. , here are the results of the data normality test:

Table 2 Normality Test

Variable	Sig	Information
X	0.57	Normal

The basis for collecting decisions is based on probability (*Asyotic Significance*), namely:

1. If the probability is > 0.05 the data is normally distributed
2. If the probability < 0.05 the data is not normally distributed

Based on the table of normality test results, *the Asyotic Significance* is 0.57. The value is $0.57 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the variable role of parents and schools in student learning motivation is normally distributed.

- b. To carry out a data linearity test, the author carried out a test using the SPSS 26 application. The results of this data linearity test are:

Table 3 Linearity Test

Variable	Sig
X	0.82

Based on table 4.1 above, it can be seen and concluded that the highest score is 78 and the lowest is 38.

Instrument Trial Results

1. Validity Test

1. Test the validity of the influence of the role of parents and school

To test validity, researchers used the SPSS program. For the level of validity, a significant test is carried out by comparing r_{count} with the r_{table} value, where if r_{count} is greater than r_{table} , that is, r_{count} for each statement item is greater than 0.361, namely r_{table} . So it can be concluded that the questionnaire used by researchers in collecting data is valid.

2. Validity Test Results Student learning motivation

To test validity, researchers used the SPSS program. For the level of validity, a significant test is carried out by comparing the r_{count} with the r_{table} value, where if the r_{count} is greater than r_{table} then the statement item is said to be valid, that is, the r_{count} for each statement item is greater than 0.361, namely r_{table} . So it can be concluded that the questionnaire used by researchers in collecting data is valid.

Reliability Test Results

Through Cronbach's Alpha $r_{count} > [r_{table}]$ _which is $0.90 > 0.87$. From the results of the reliability test calculations, there is an influence on the role of parents and schools. It can be concluded that the research instruments used in this research are reliable.

Prerequisite Test Results

a. Data Normality Test

Based on the results of the data normality test using SPSS 22, it is presented in the table below:

Table 4
Normality Test of the Influence of the Role of Parents and Schools on Learning Motivation

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test			
		Lingkunga n Sekolah	Motivasi Belajar
N		30	30
Normal Parameter s ^{a,b}	Mean	57,80	62,57
	Std. Deviation	10,226	9,811
Most Extreme Difference s	Absolute	,131	,131
	Positive	,131	,116
	Negative	-,084	-,131
Kolmogorov-Smirnov		,718	,716
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,680	,684

a. Test distribution is Normal.
b. Calculated from data.

Based on the table above, the Normality test on school environment variables (X) learning motivation (Y) is based on statistical test values of 0.718 and 0.716. Next, this value is compared with the regulatory value of 0.05. So the statistical test value was obtained greater than the provisions ($0.718 > 0.05$) and ($0.716 > 0.05$). So it can be concluded that the data is concluded from the influence of the role of normal parents and school (X) on normal student learning motivation (Y).

b. Linearity Test

Based on the results of the linearity test, the influence of the role of parents and schools on student learning motivation using SPSS 26 is presented in the table below:

Table 5
Linearity Test of the Influence of the Role of Parents and Schools on Learning Motivation
ANOVA Table

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Learning Motivatio n *Influence of the Role of Parents and Schools	Between Groups	(Combined)	2612,45 0	18	145,136	8,923	,000
		Linearity	1394,34 9	1	1394,34 9	85,726	,000
		Deviation from Linearity	1218,10 1	17	71,653	4,405	,008
	Within Groups		178,917	11	16,265		
	Total		2791,36 7	29			

Based on table 5 above, the values obtained $F_{\text{count}} = 4.405$, while the $F_{\text{table value}} = 2.97$ for $df_1 = 17$ and $df_2 = 11$ at the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ so that $F_{\text{count}} < F_{\text{table}}$. Thus, it can be concluded that student learning motivation has a linear relationship.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Homogeneity tests were carried out, data hypothesis testing was carried out. Hypothesis data testing serves to determine the influence of the role of parents and schools on learning motivation. The following are the results of the hypothesis test below :

Table 6
Hypothesis Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Q	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	23,375	7,525		3,106	,004
Influence of the Role of Parents and Schools	,678	,128	,707	5,286	,000

Based on table above you can see a significance of 0.000. Because significance is smaller than 0.05, H_0 is rejected. Which means there is a significant influence between the school environment and the learning motivation of class V students at SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak .

Hypothesis F Test

The F test aims to determine whether or not there is a relationship given by the independent variable (x) to the dependent variable (y).

Table 7
Test (f) ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	1394,349	1	1394,349	27,947	,000 ^b
Residual	1397,018	28	49,893		
Total	2791,367	29			

Based on the table above, it is known that the significant value for the relationship of variable (x) simultaneously to y is $0.00 < 0.05$ and the f_{count} value is $27.947 > 4.20$ (f table) so it can be concluded that the hypothesis test is accepted which means there is simultaneous relationship between variable (x) and variable (y).

4.1 Coefficient of Determination Test

The coefficient of determination aims to describe the magnitude of the relationship between the school environment and students' learning motivation in class V of Pematangsiantar R2 Pilot Elementary School, called the coefficient of determination or determining coefficient.

Table 8
Determination Coefficient Test Results

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.707 ^a	.500	.482	7,064
a. Predictors: (Constant), Influence of the Role of Parents and School				

Based on the table above, it can be concluded that based on the SPSS output results, the coefficient of determination or r square value is 0.500. This means that the relationship between variable (x) and variable (y) simultaneously is 50.0% and can be proven by other variables such as: motivation student learning.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of research conducted at SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak for the 2022/2023 academic year, Tapian Dolok District, North Sumatra Province regarding the Influence of the Role of Parents and Schools on Student Learning Motivation. In this research, the questionnaire instrument distributed to respondents, namely fifth grade elementary school students, has been tested for validation and reliability, consisting of 25 questionnaires on the Influence of the Role of Parents and Schools and 25 valid and reliable learning motivation questionnaires.

The results of the t test hypothesis testing using SPSS conclude that learning motivation has a significant effect on the school environment. This can be seen in table 4. 9 where the t and sig columns describe that learning motivation is at 0.00, which means it is smaller than 0.05, this shows that learning motivation has a significant influence on the school environment. This illustrates that student learning motivation is influenced by the school environment in the good category. Students who are influenced by a good school environment will also have high motivation to learn. Meanwhile, students with low influence from the school environment will also have low motivation to learn.

Learning motivation means encouragement from students to achieve learning goals, for example understanding material or developing learning. With motivation, students will always be enthusiastic to continue learning without any coercion from any party. How to grow it is certainly not an easy matter because each student has different characters and desires. This is of course not entirely the teacher's responsibility, but you still play an important role in it.

Types of Learning Motivation

Student learning motivation can be divided into two types, namely as follows.

1. Intrinsic Learning Motivation : Intrinsic motivation is motivation that comes from students themselves to learn. This motivation can be influenced by the student's desire to achieve a certain goal, for example to excel, enter a favorite school, enter a favorite college, make their parents proud, and so on.
2. Extrinsic Learning Motivation: Extrinsic motivation is motivation that comes from outside, for example the environment. Examples of extrinsic motivation are the promise of prizes from parents if you excel, following suggestions or advice from teachers, and so on. The ways to improve it are as follows:
 - Convey motivation directly. One way to increase student motivation is to motivate them. In the previous points, the motivation that you gave was indirect motivation.
 - *Students' Goals or Aspirations* : Motivation to learn can be seen in children's desires from childhood. Success in achieving your desires can foster a willingness to learn which will give rise to goals in life. Dreams can strengthen intrinsic and extrinsic motivation.
 - *Student Will* , A child's desire needs to be accompanied by the ability to achieve it, because desire will strengthen the child's motivation to carry out developmental tasks.
 - *Student Conditions* : Student conditions which include physical and spiritual conditions influence learning motivation.
 - *Students' environmental conditions* : Students can be influenced by the surrounding environment, therefore the quality of a healthy school

environment, harmony and social order need to be improved so that students' enthusiasm and motivation to learn can be easily strengthened.

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Based on the results of the researchers' influence on the role of parents on school and student learning motivation in class V of SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak, it can be concluded that:

1. The influence of the role of parents on students' learning motivation in class V, research is 0.37 so it can be concluded that, there is an influence of the role of parents on learning motivation, but it is not that high.
2. The role of parents and teachers has an influence on the learning motivation of fifth grade students at SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak. This can be seen from the results of the hypothesis test.

Recommendations

Based on this research, the researcher provides the following suggestions

1. For Students

The results of this research can provide understanding and apply knowledge about the important role of parents and schools which have a positive impact on children's learning outcomes.

2. For Parents

The results of this research can be used to provide knowledge about the importance of parental attention to children's learning motivation at school both in terms of emotions and completeness in learning as well as in managing study time for children to get maximum results in their learning.

3. For Teachers

The results of this research are usually used as evaluation material in providing guidance and counseling services to be motivated to learn so that learning objectives can be achieved optimally.

3. For School Principals

The results of this research can be used as information about parents regarding learning outcomes, so that they are expected to provide appropriate policies in increasing students' learning motivation, both at school and at home and in the school environment.

4. For Researchers

The results of this research are only limited to parents' attention, therefore for students who will carry out research, research needs to be conducted on the aspect of having other factors that also influence learning motivation apart from the role of parents and school.

REFERENCES

- Amin, Suci, Rini Harianti, *The Influence of the Role of Parents and Schools on Student Learning Motivation* , (Yogyakarta: Budi Utama, 2018)
- Annuraga, Heng Hangesti *The Role of Parents in Increasing Learning Motivation for Students Aged 6-12 Years (Case Study of the Home Visit Program at Dolan Malang Homeschooling School)*, "Out-of-School Education, Faculty of Education, UNESA7. No. 3(2018),
- Arikunto, Suharsimi. *Research Procedures a Practical Approach* , (Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta, 2006
- Cahyani, Adhetya, Lin Diah Listiana, Sari Puteri Deta Lestari, *High School Students' Learning Motivation in Online Learning during the Covid-19 Pandemic* , Journal of Islamic Education Vol. 3No. 012020,P. 123-140ISSN:2338-4131
- Djamarah, Syaiful Bahri *Communication Patterns of Parents & Children in the Family An Islamic Education Perspective* , (Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta, 2004)
- Amin, Suci, Rini Harianti, *Parenting Patterns in Children's Learning Motivation* , (Yogyakarta: Budi Utama, 2018)
- Annuraga, Hening Hangesti *The Role of Parents in Increasing Learning Motivation for Students Aged 6-12 Years (Case Study of the HomeVisit Program at Dolan Malang Homeschooling School)*, "Out-of-School Education, Faculty of Education, UNESA7, No. 3 (2018)
- Arikunto, Suharsimi *Research Procedures a Practical Approach* , (Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta, 2006)
- Cahyani, Adhetya, Lin Diah Listiana, Sari Puteri Deta Lestari, *High School Students' Learning Motivation in Online Learning during the Covid-19 Pandemic* , Journal of Islamic Education Vol. 3No. 012020,P. 123-140ISSN:2338-4131
- Djamarah, Syaiful Bahri *Communication Patterns between Parents & Children in Family A Perspective on Islamic Education* , (Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta, 2004)

Djamarah, Syaiful Bahri *Psychology of Learning* , (Jakarta: Rineka Cipta, 2011), Endriani, Ani, *The Relationship between Parental Attention and Learning Motivation in Class VIII SMPN6 Students, East Praya, Central Lombok Lesson 2015/2016* , Jurnal Realita, Vol. 1 Number 2 October 2016 Edition, ISSN (250-1708)